

Hourly based methods to assess carbon footprint flexibility and primary energy use in decarbonized buildings

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ABSTRACT

Constant emission factors to assess the carbon footprint of buildings energy use, as usually included in national Building Technical Codes, show their limitations since the electrical grid mix changes constantly. For this reason, hourly-based methods using time-varying penalty signals to calculate carbon emissions and primary energy use in buildings constitute more effective assessment methods, especially with the aim to activate energy flexibility in buildings based on those inputs. Such signals have been developed and tested in the present work. The robustness and effectiveness of the methods is tested throughout two study cases. The first case compares the impact of using hourly signals over constant factors from the standards. For that purpose, a measured aggregated consumption profile corresponding to 226 real households is analyzed. In the second study case, demand response is implemented through control strategies reacting to the hourly penalty signals, aiming to decrease the emissions, primary energy use and cost. Results for the first case reveal that hourly rates better capture the variability of the electric grid compared to constant yearly factors from national standards, with a 50% difference in carbon emissions and a 20% overestimation with primary energy. Results from the second study case show how the implemented modulation strategies offer benefits in the flexible scenarios compared to the base scenarios, in terms of accumulated emissions or primary energy. Improvements are especially perceived when splitting data seasonally and considering periods with higher demand. Furthermore, this study provides insights for developing energy flexibility inputs when assessing the building performance during critical events such as the COVID19 pandemic or extreme weather conditions, where hourly and seasonal variation might have greater impact. Demand response mechanisms as energy flexibility strategies studied through this work might help in the reduction of total emissions and primary energy. Depending if the goal is to shift the demand due to environmental or economical reasons, different modulation strategies can be implemented to reach greater benefits.

KEYWORDS: Demand response mechanisms, Energy flexibility in buildings, Household energy consumption, Hourly conversion factors, Carbon emissions, Primary energy use

39 1 INTRODUCTION

40 Buildings represent 32% of the total final energy consumption in the world contributing to the
41 largest proportion of CO₂ emissions compared to other sectors, therefore the impact during the
42 operational lifetime should be evaluated precisely. The European Union strives for sharp
43 reductions in both its primary energy use and carbon emissions, as formalized in the flagship 2030
44 policy targets and the associated legislation – including the Energy Performance of Buildings
45 Directive (EPBD, 2018) and the Energy Efficiency Directive (EED, 2018). Reaching these targets
46 requires an accurate assessment of how different technologies perform on these two fronts.

47 To calculate the primary energy and CO₂ emissions associated with the consumption of electricity,
48 conversion factors are required, namely a primary energy factor (PEF) and a carbon emissions
49 factor (AEF). National entities provide values of these conversion factors in their building
50 assessment codes, which allow to characterize the emissions and primary energy from a building
51 electricity consumption. However, the factors associated with all energy carriers including
52 electricity are considered as constant values through the whole year. Consequently, they do not
53 capture the daily or seasonal variations of the grid operation, so they can misjudge the estimation
54 of the carbon emissions and primary energy. Moreover, the conversion factors are not frequently
55 updated: for instance factors from the building assessment in Spanish codes were last updated in
56 2014 (RITE).

57 In this sense, as pointed by (Hamels et al., 2021) there is still a strong need in literature for a
58 publicly available and methodologically transparent database of up-to-date electricity conversion
59 factors for emissions and primary energy. There are existing methodologies such as the one
60 provided by the Spanish Transmission System Operator Red Electrica de España (REE), that
61 computes hourly emissions from electricity generation. The gap lays on a need for a detailed hourly
62 calculation of primary energy conversion factors. An hourly calculation would capture the
63 variability happening in the electricity grid at various time scales (seasonally, daily and hourly),
64 which becomes even more relevant as the penetration of renewables increases in the energy mix.
65 There is no visibility thus far on the difference it makes to compute the impact of building
66 operation with constant factors or through more accurate hourly calculations.

67 Accurate values of the emissions and primary energy use of the electricity grid on an hourly
68 temporal resolution are also important for energy flexibility in buildings and to activate demand
69 response strategies. Demand response involves shifting electricity demand to provide flexibility in
70 wholesale and ancillary power markets, helping to balance the grid when renewables have high
71 levels of penetration (IEA, 2022). Consumers can then make intentional choices to organize their
72 energy consumption around times of the day when energy is being produced by renewable energy
73 sources (RES), for instance increasing their demand when there is more clean energy on the grid.
74 In this sense, (Klein, 2016) studies how heat pumps and chillers should be operated in order to
75 make the best use of the volatile renewable energy simulating and analyzing the residual load in
76 the year of 2030 which is the electricity demand that is not covered with intermittent RES and
77 must be met by dispatchable electricity generation units.

78 The hourly signals of emissions or primary energy in the grid might serve as inputs to energy
79 flexibility and demand response strategies, establishing which periods are more favourable
80 according to one criteria or the other. These periods must be defined according to environmental,
81 economic or energetic penalty perspective (Fitzpatrick et al., 2020; Marotta et al., 2021; Mugnini
82 et al., 2021; Péan et al., 2019; Péan et al., 2017). Smart control strategies can then act on those
83 signals, but part of the intelligence and decision making resides in the fabrication of the signal
84 itself, hence the importance of the accuracy of the hourly assessment, which gives room for load
85 shifting and optimization. Such technologies are crucial as they enable and offer higher flexibility
86 potential although their deployment is still lagging behind (Li et al., 2022).

87 Other works have studied signals representing the grid operation at hourly or sub-hourly
88 resolution. Biéron et al. (2023) focused their approach on identifying the marginal technology in
89 the French grid which would be sensitive to demand response actions. Gagnon and Cole (2022)
90 estimated hourly emissions in the US, including the long-run effect of structural impacts (changes
91 in the energy mix). Hamels et al. (2021) provided a review of primary energy and CO₂ emissions
92 factors used in the literature, and highlighted that most of them have yearly resolution. Hourly
93 emissions are often computed but it is not necessarily the case for primary energy.

94 The present work also aims to contribute at designing resilient communities to fight future
95 pandemic crises and face climate change extreme events. Hourly and seasonal variation have
96 greater impact throughout these periods of unusual activity, disrupted periods either by
97 meteorological extreme events (becoming more prevalent due to climate change) or others, i.e.
98 COVID19 lockdown, a scenario where the demand experienced a large shift.

99 *Objectives*

100 The main purpose of this article is to investigate the potential of applying hourly dynamic emission
101 and primary energy conversion factors to assess and optimize the energy use of buildings. Using
102 dynamic factor instead of using yearly average factor will encourage to shift buildings electricity
103 consumption when there is less greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and primary energy use in the
104 system, by means of appropriate design and/or operations. To justify and showcase the use of hourly
105 average rates, technology and country-specific factors are retrieved from different sources and
106 used for computation, leading to a different view of the significance of interventions than using
107 yearly average rates. The impact of the proposed methodology in the overall carbon emissions and
108 primary energy have been analysed with real consumption data for complete years in the period
109 2018-2021, as well as for specific and relevant periods related with disruptions in the residential
110 energy consumption: periods in the vicinity of COVID19 crisis and climate change related events
111 such as heat waves and snow storms. It is expected that accurate characterization of conversion
112 factors and hourly calculation will produce better assessment of buildings impact in specific
113 periods or complete years. This might help to design adaptive measures in the building
114 environment that allow resilient buildings to face future challenges and an increasing penetration
115 of RES in the electricity grid.

116 The additional aim of the paper is to showcase the use of hourly conversion factors as a means of
117 activating energy flexibility in buildings' operation. Demand response is implemented throughout
118 this study as simple control strategies based on modulation signals reacting to hourly penalty
119 signals. It aims to decrease CO₂ emissions and primary energy computed with the hourly signals,
120 incentivized by the produced modulation signals.

121 The article is structured as follows: the first section presents the methodology as a guidance of the
122 steps followed to compute the hourly signals, to retrieve the hourly conversion factors from the
123 operation of the electricity system and the price signal. It is followed by a description of the
124 consumption profile used and the demand response indicators and flexibility key performance
125 indicators (KPIs). Following, two scenarios are studied: a scenario based on monitored
126 consumption profiles from 226 households (Case 1) and a simulation scenario to implement energy
127 flexibility strategies through the use of dynamic building models (Case 2). Energy, carbon
128 emissions and primary energy impact are analyzed for both scenarios in the results section,
129 highlighting specific results for each scenario. Finally, results are discussed and final remarks and
130 conclusions are exposed in the last two sections, including proposal for further research work.

131 **NOMENCLATURE**

AEF	Average carbon emissions factor per period, expressed in kgCO ₂ /kWh
APEFnr	Average non-renewable primary energy use factor, expressed in kWpe/kWh
BC	Building assessment codes
CE	Carbon emissions
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CI	CO ₂ intensity of electricity, expressed in kgCO ₂ /kWh
CFs	Conversion factors
DR	Demand-response
EC	Energy cost, expressed in EUR
EEA	European Environmental Agency
EF	Emissions factor for specific fuel, expressed in kgCO ₂ /kWh
IEA	International Energy Agency
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change established by the UNFCCC
kCO ₂ eq.	Equivalent CO ₂ emissions, expressed in kCO ₂ eq.

kWh _{pe eq.}	Equivalent PE use, expressed in kWh _{pe eq.}
kWh _E	Kilowatt hour of electricity
PE	Primary energy (use) expressed in kWh _{pe} (associated with a particular appliance)
PEF	Primary energy factor for specific fuel, expressed in kWh _{pe} /kWh _{fe}
PVPC	Volunteer price to small consumers, expressed in EUR/kWh
RES	Renewable energy sources
TR	Temporal resolution
TS	Temporal scope
TSO	Transmission system operator
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

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2 METHODOLOGY

137 The methodology explained in this section can be directly used to compute hourly electricity
138 carbon emissions, primary energy, renewables and price signals. In this sense, this methodology
139 is applied to investigate the potential of hourly temporal resolution signals as inputs to activate
140 demand response mechanisms such as energy flexibility in buildings. Three main steps are
141 followed: first, hourly signals are either retrieved directly (price) or computed from downloaded
142 inputs (Average emissions factor (AEF), primary energy factor (PEF) and percentage of renewable
143 energy sources (RES)). Second, conversion factors from the building code are retrieved for
144 comparison. Third, the flexibility strategy is defined and performance indicators are described.

145 Figure 1 showcases the methodological process and the application to case studies.. Two case
146 studies are used: in Case 1, the impact when making use of hourly average rate compared to factors
147 retrieved from the building codes (constant year values) is investigated, using real historical data
148 from monitored households. Secondly, Case 2 investigates the potential of using these signals as
149 inputs to activate energy flexibility in buildings and what is the benefit of implementing a flexible
150 scenario for each signal modulation compared to the base case, using simulation models.

Figure 1: Methodology flowchart.

151

152 *2.1 Hourly signals*

153 The construction of hourly signals as a time series of the electricity grid can be used as an effective
 154 method to activate demand-side strategies in buildings and thus reducing their carbon footprint
 155 and non-renewable primary energy use. Contrary to constant factors retrieved from building
 156 assessment codes, they capture the variability of the electrical grid.

157 **Data**

158 Historical data were retrieved from the public API of the Spanish TSO ESIOS (ESIOS, 2022) to
 159 compute the hourly signals. The detailed methodology can be found in (Alvarez, Péan, & Salom,
 160 2022). It has been applied to compute the hourly signals for CO₂ emissions and primary energy
 161 use for the time period considered in this study (January 1st 2018 to December 31st 2021).

162 **Conversion factors**

163 Technology-specific and country-specific conversion factors have been retrieved from different
 164 sources (see Table 1). They enable the conversion of the generated energy into CO₂ emissions or
 165 primary energy. They are used to compute the average factors per hour also named in this study as
 166 hourly penalty signals (AEF and APEF) described in sections 2.1.1 and 2.1.2.

Table 1: Conversion factors (emissions and primary energy use) for specific electricity generation technologies.

		EF		PEF			Source
		kgCO ₂ /kWh		Total	Non-renewable	Renewable	
Sources		Value	Source	kWh _{pe,tot} /kWh	kWh _{pe,ren} /kWh	kWh _{pe,ren} /kWh	
Non-Renewable	Nuclear	0.012	[1]	3.26	3.21	0.05	[8]
	Coal	1.210	[1]	2.25	2.25	0	[8]
	Combined Gas Cycle	0.492	[1]	1.88	1.85	0.03	[8]
	Natural Gas Cogeneration	0.380	[2]	1.8	1.76	0.04	[8]
	Fuel	0.866	[1]	2.73	2.54	0.19	[7]
Renewable	Wind	0.014	[1]	1.02	0.02	1	[8]
	Photovoltaic	0.071	[1]	1.1	0.07	1.03	[8]
	Solar Thermal	0.027	[3]	1.03	0.03	1	[6]
	Ocean/Geothermal	0.082	[1]	1.34	0.21	1.13	[8]
	Biomass	0.054	[1]	1.473	1.393	0.080	[5]
	Biogas	0.018	[4]	2.7	0.15	2.55	[8]
	Waste RSU	0.240	[2]	1.473	1.393	0.080	[5]
	Hydro UGH reservoir	0.024	[1]	1.078	0.1	0.978	[7]
Hydro non UGH	0.004	[1]					

	Pumped Hydro storage	0.062	[1]	1.69	1.69	0	[7]
	France	0.068	[1]	2.767	2.447	0.32	[1]
Imports	Portugal	0.484	[1]	1.967	1.728	0.24	[1]
	Morocco	0.729	[1]	1.856	0.902	0.955	[1]

Note: Annual (constant) average values. References: [1] (Tranberg, 2019), [2] (ESIOS, 2022), [3] (IPCC Annex III, 2014), [4] (IPCC Annex II, 2014), [5] (IDAE, 2014), [6] (EU,), [7] (IPCC, 2011), [8] (IINAS, 2020).

167 In this respect, it is noted that it was decided to show the original sources from where the
168 conversion factors were retrieved. In Table 1, it is observed that factors from sources back in 2014
169 or less correspond to the following technologies:

- 170 • Solar thermal (IPCC, 2014) and biogas (IPCC, 2014) (emissions)
- 171 • Fuel (IPCC, 2011), biomass (IDAE, 2014), waste RSU (IDAE, 2014), hydro (IPCC, 2011)
- 172 and pumped hydro (IPCC, 2011) (primary energy).

173 Although some conversion factors for these technologies was found in reports from reliable
174 sources published recently, (IPCC (2022), IPCC (2019), IPCC (2023), ESIOS (2021), Real
175 Decreto 238/2013, Real Decreto 413/2014, Real Decreto 178/2021, Reglamento (UE) 601/2012),
176 original sources are from scientific published work from 2014 or before. The conversion factors
177 by each technology is linked to the actual electricity producing devices and systems and/or the use
178 of certain energy carriers. For mature technologies, their operation have not evolved so importantly
179 as to make their emissions or primary energy factors change dramatically.

180

181 **Energy balance**

182 The energy balance between consumption and generation in the electricity network is computed
183 hourly. The generation demand is shown in Eq. (1) and the consumption demand in Eq. (2), where
184 $D_{b.c.}$ is the generation demand; $E_{b.c.}$ is the sum of the renewables (G_r), non-renewables (G_{nr}),
185 turbine consumption (C_{tb}) and balearic link (B_l); Interconnections exchange is represented by I_e ,
186 consumption demand by DC and L are the grid losses:

$$187 \quad D_{b.c.} = E_{b.c.} + I_e = G_r + G_{nr} - C_{tb} - B_l + I_e \quad (1)$$

$$188 \quad DC = D_{b.c.} - L \quad (2)$$

189 The need to perform this balance lies on the purpose of these signals as well as the data available
190 by the Spanish TSO. The hourly electricity signals enable strategies to manage the consumption
191 demand at a concrete moment, thus reducing the carbon footprint and use of primary energy of the
192 built environment. Consumption demand is the final demand allowing to manage it properly, as it
193 accounts for the variable performance of the electric grid. In this sense, ESIOS provides the

194 generation of electricity $E_{b.c.}$ and the other indicators, where the consumption demand is not
195 provided then must be computed.

196 2.1.1. Hourly electricity carbon emissions (CE) signal

197 A hourly carbon emissions signal represents the carbon footprint of the power grid (attending to
198 its variability), representing time-varying carbon emissions of the different energy sources in the
199 electricity mix, differentiating between hours of low or high emissions. It can be considered as
200 input for demand-side management schemes such as activation energy flexibility in buildings
201 (Péan, 2018).

202 The CO₂ emission factor at hour h, units in [kgCO₂/kWh] is defined as:

$$203 \quad EF_h^{CO_2} = \frac{\sum(E_{b.c.s/h}) \times EF_s^{CO_2}}{DC_h} \quad (3)$$

204

205 2.1.2 Hourly electricity primary energy (PE) use signal

206 An hourly non-renewable primary energy use signal represents time-varying use of energy from
207 non-renewable sources that are being used in the mix, which informs hours of lower use of these
208 technologies.

209 The primary energy factor at hour h, units in [kWh_{pe}/kWh] is defined as:

$$210 \quad PEF_h = \frac{\sum(E_{b.c.s/h}) \times PEF_s}{DC_h} \quad (4)$$

211

212

213

214 2.1.3 Hourly electricity price signal

215 In Spain the electricity price is provided hourly by the TSO (ESIOS, 2022). This is a variable hourly
216 tariff named “Volunteer price to small consumers” (PVPC) that is applied to small consumers with
217 a contracted power of less than 10kW (before June 2021) and less than 15kW (since then). Before
218 June 2021 it had 2 periods of application and now it has 3 periods (peak, medium and valley hours
219 for residential consumers).

220 The PVPC signal, which information being published daily at 20:20 hours within the day-ahead,
221 can act as a mechanism that enables consumers to directly shift their demand for electricity at times
222 of the day with lower energy costs.

223 2.1.4 Hourly electricity RES signal

224 The ratio of renewables is computed. RES – E ratio measures the contribution of electricity
 225 produced from renewables to the national electricity consumption. It comprises the generation
 226 from renewable plants (excluding pumping) (Eurostat, 2008). The ratio of renewables is computed
 227 as shown in Eq. (5), where $\sum G_r$ is the generation from renewables and $\sum G_{nr}$ from non-renewables:

$$228 \quad RES - E = \frac{\sum G_r}{\sum G_r + \sum G_{nr}} \quad (5)$$

230

231 2.2 Factors from building assessment codes

232 Table 2 presents the factors retrieved from the building assessment codes (IDAE, 2014). They are
 233 system average rates from national governments that allow us to compute emissions [kgCO₂/kWh]
 234 and primary energy [kWh_{pe}/kWh] rates. Indeed, they are characterized for being constant over
 235 different period and period subsets, finding that we would have the same conversion factor to
 236 assess CE and PE no matter what the variability of the electric grid and specific-period
 237 circumstances. For instance, for periods where the RES penetration is higher, in the computation
 238 of the associated emissions with this factor we would have overestimated the CE as we would not
 239 have considered the accurate set of technologies that produces electricity in that specific period.

Table 2: Conversion factors from building assessment codes (yearly annual values) for electricity in Spain.

	EF		PEF					
	kgCO ₂ /kWh		Total		Non-renewable		Renewable	
			kWh _{pe,tot} /kWh		kWh _{pe,nren} /kWh		kWh _{pe,ren} /kWh	
System	N	E	N	E	N	E	N	E
Building codes	0.33	0.83	2.37	3.01	1.95	2.94	0.41	0.08

Note: source for references (IDAE, 2014). Factors are differentiated by national (N) which refers to peninsular conventional electricity and extrapeninsular (E) which refers to conventional electricity in Baleares, Canarias, Ceuta and Melilla.

240 2.3 Demand response

241 This paper also presents the methods for implementing demand response mechanisms such as
 242 energy flexibility in buildings. The aim of the study is to activate the energy flexibility of the
 243 analysis building through time-varying penalty signals. To implement flexibility strategies in a
 244 based-simulation case study the followed steps are detailed hereafter:

- 245 1. Hourly signals (CE, PE and PVPC) are retrieved for one year (2018).
- 246 2. In the simulation software TRNSYS, as input is given, a control strategy for each signal is
- 247 defined

- 248 a. Development of a building model with type and data declared in Section 3.2
 249 b. Defined the control strategies to activate energy flexibility using the time-varying
 250 penalty signals and implement them in the model
 251 3. Simulation
 252 a. Simulation of the defined scenarios
 253 b. Analysis of the impact of different actions that activate energy flexibility in
 254 buildings through control strategies in HVAC systems

255 Strategies involving this concept might face the challenges highlighted by the European energy
 256 transition “the way we use energy”, helping in a reduction in GHG emissions and PE use. In cases
 257 such as the ones studied throughout this paper, heating and cooling loads in buildings are mainly
 258 covered by electricity where flexibility strategies might be implemented. Through smart grid
 259 control algorithms, demand response mechanisms might be implemented to help in the GHG and
 260 PE estimation and thus, reduction. Through these strategies, a user (being the smart control) can
 261 modify its consumption when there is RES available in the system, and be penalized at times where
 262 there is little available, thus, the so-called time-varying penalty signals.

263 2.3.1. Building performance indicators: accumulated penalty units

264 The accumulated penalty units are studied using the hourly factors and factors from building
 265 assessment codes to assess the difference. Accumulated penalty units investigated are:

- 266 • **[CE]**: The accumulated electricity use expressed in kWh
- 267 • **[CAEF]**: The accumulated CO2 emissions expressed in kgCO2
- 268 • **[CAPEF]**: The accumulated Primary energy expressed in kWh_pe
- 269 • **[CPVPC]**: The accumulated Energy cost expressed in EUR

270 2.3.2. Energy flexibility KPIs: flexibility index

271 Flexibility index symbolizes the fractional savings that is possible to achieve when applying the
 272 flexibility control strategy, compared to a base case scenario. Flexibility index 0 symbolizes zero
 273 improvement in the flexibility scenario, meaning that both the base and flexible case had equal
 274 amounts of penalties. Flexibility index 1 indicates that the flexible case accumulated penalty is
 275 close to 0 (R. G. Junker et al.). The flexibility index (FI) shown in Eq. (1) and the penalty unit (C_n)
 276 in Eq. (4), where C_1 is the accumulated penalty of flexible case (penalty unit) and C_0 the
 277 accumulated penalty of base case (penalty unit), and E representing energy consumption (kWh)
 278 and λ the penalty signal (penalty unit/kWh).

$$279 \quad FI = 1 - \frac{C_1}{C_0} \quad (6)$$

$$280 \quad C_n = \sum(E_t \times \lambda_t) \quad (7)$$

281

282 **3 DESCRIPTION OF CASE STUDIES**

283 In this section the case studies proposed to test the hourly signals are described (see Table 3). Each
 284 case study is oriented to a specific phase in order to study the effectiveness of the methodology.
 285 On one hand, Case 1 analyzes a summarized consumption profile from different residential
 286 buildings in Barcelona (Spain) measured from 2018 to 2021. The consumption curve refers to an
 287 aggregated consumption corresponding to 226 households with a contracted power ranging from
 288 4.1 to 5 kW. The contracted power for this case has been selected for being the most representative
 289 parameter on which to select a large number of households with similar characteristics. Its aim is
 290 to compare the difference of estimating the CE and PE with hourly signals or applying the values
 291 from building assessment codes. On the other hand, Case 2 simulates a single flat in the climate of
 292 Barcelona with 4.3 kW contracted power, hence also in a similar range than the real data from
 293 Case 1. Using a dynamic model to generate data of the simulated household, modulation strategies
 294 are applied based on the hourly signals for the whole year of 2018 with the aim to assess their
 295 accumulated CE and PE and test benefits from flexibility scenarios.

Table 3: The corresponding information and parameters of studied cases.

Study Cases	Case 1	Case 2
Objective	Hourly based methods vs. factors from building assessment codes	Energy flexibility control strategies
Type	Real measured values	Simulated values
Data considered	Representative (aggregated) summarized profile	TRNSYS consumption profile
Household	226 households consumption profiles	1 Single flat (within block of flat)
Contracted power	4.1 – 5 kW	4.3 kW
Location	Barcelona	Barcelona

296

297 *3.1. Case 1: Real values scenario*

298 Figure 2a showcases the aggregated consumption profiles with hourly temporal resolution of the
 299 226 buildings from January 1st 2018 to December 31st 2021. Data has hourly temporal resolution.
 300 It is observed the impact of the particular period of COVID19 pandemic and lockdown (2020),
 301 presenting higher consumption demand during the morning.

Figure 2a: Summarized consumption profile (hourly mean per year) for Case 1.

302

303 Additionally, Figure 2b shows how the profiles vary per season. In this sense, a significant month
 304 have been used to represent every season: January (winter), April (spring), July (summer) and
 305 October (Autumm).

306

307 Figure 2b: Summary of consumption profiles per month (season representative).

308 There is a notable consumption shift in April 2020 when the pandemic started. The actual range
 309 dates for the pandemic, from 14th March to August 7th, leaving a post-pandemic period afterwards
 310 with the corresponding effect on consumption behavior.

311

312 3.1.1 Analysis periods for Case 1

313 This study has a focus to determine how the computation of hourly signals impact the final
 314 estimation of a building consumption associated with emissions or primary energy use. Therefore,
 315 by selecting diverse events as periods of analysis (see Table 4) the behavior of these signals can
 316 be determined over periods of unusual activity, disrupted periods affected by COVID or extreme
 317 climate events. Hourly and seasonal variation might have greater impact throughout these periods
 318 where there is a difference in the demand of electricity.

Table 4: Periods of analysis and RES share [%] for Case 1.

Period	Dates	Year	Share of RES [%]
Heat wave	July 29 th – August 11 th	2018	34.31
Pre-pandemic	March 14 th – August 7 th	2019	36.87
Pandemic	March 14 th – August 7 th	2020	45.96
Post-pandemic	March 14 th – August 7 th	2021	49.31
Intense snow	January 9 th – January 10 th	2021	53.65

319

320 Table 4 shows there is an increase of RES as years pass by. It can be also appreciated that the use
 321 of fossil fuel technologies with relatively lower emission factors are increasing their use, where
 322 additionally these technologies are improving their efficiency contributing to lower emissions.

323 3.2. Case 2: Simulation scenario

324 3.2.1 Meteorological data

325 Historical weather data from 2018 is provided by the meteorological station of the “Servei
 326 Meteorològic de Catalunya ” (meteocat, 2022a) of “Badalona Museu”, located close to Barcelona
 327 municipality. The period selected for simulation would be throughout the year of 2018.

328 3.2.2 Building data

329 The building for this case study is simulated with a dynamic model set up in the TRNSYS software.
 330 Its main characteristics are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Building model used for Case 2.

Type of building	1 Single flat (within block of flat) of 90 m2 with three occupants
Model type	TRNSYS Type56+systems. Typology F by the Catalan Housing Agency (AHC, 2014)
Location	Barcelona center
Timestep	1 minute (resampled hourly)
System	Air-to-water heat pump coupled with radiant floor for heating, fancoils for cooling

331

332 3.2.3 Input signals and flexibility strategy

333 The flexibility strategies implemented depend on the inputs that activate them. The hourly signals
334 developed and implemented for Case 1 are used here. The signals considered are the hourly CE,
335 PE, PVPC and RES, corresponding to the year 2018.

336 The flexibility strategy consists in modulating the indoor temperature set-point in the building
337 model, depending on the current value of the input penalty signal previously chosen among the
338 four options previously mentioned. This modulation is carried out as follows:

- 339 ● Low-penalty: +1: If value < 25th percentile of next-day values
 - 340 ○ When threshold passed, the reference set-point is modulated with an amplitude of
 - 341 1°C [+ 1°C (heating) and -1°C (cooling)]
 - 342 ● High-penalty: -1: If value > 25th percentile of next-day values
 - 343 ○ When threshold passed, the reference set-point is modulated with an amplitude of
 - 344 1°C [+ 1°C (cooling) and -1°C (heating)]
 - 345 ● Absence of penalty: 0, set-point unchanged
- 346

347 4 RESULTS

348 Results are presented hereafter in three sections. The first section 4.1. presents the computed hourly
349 signals compared to factors from building assessment codes. The 4.2. and 4.3. sections present the
350 results for Case 1 and Case 2 respectively.

351 4.1. Hourly electricity signals: temporal resolution impact

352 Figure 3 presents the hourly factors computed throughout the methodology: the carbon emissions
353 expressed in [kgCO₂/kWh] and the primary energy use expressed in kWh_{pe}/kWh. They are
354 presented for each period of analysis described in 3.1.1 Analysis periods for Case 1 (Table 4).
355 Over the different periods (see legend from Figure 3), it is intended to analyze the behavior of the
356 computed hourly electricity signals in comparison to constant building codes. In Figure 3, data is
357 plotted with hourly mean per period of analysis.

Figure 3: Carbon emissions conversion factors (top) and primary energy conversion factors (bottom): average daily profiles for each period of analysis.

358

359 From Figure 3 the temporal resolution impact can be observed: while constant values from
 360 building codes do not offer variability, the computation of hourly rates does so, offering
 361 differences depending on period of analysis. To interpret the curves, high values of hourly
 362 electricity carbon emissions (CE) signal indicate more presence of fossil fuel technologies and
 363 high values of hourly electricity PE signal indicates more use of non-renewable technologies. In
 364 this sense, Figure 3 generally showcases the variability throughout the day when computing hourly
 365 signals. Indeed, the hourly electricity CE signal gets lower in observed consecutive periods. For
 366 the hourly electricity primary energy (PE) signal, it gets lower for the analysis period except for
 367 the intense snow of 2021, period in which the factor increases to levels of 2018 and 2019.

368 *4.2. Case 1*

369 The overall results for the analysis periods are presented in Table 6. Hourly conversion factors
 370 offer concrete estimations for CE and PE use over different periods. Factors retrieved from BC are
 371 constant values used as factors to assess the performance of a concrete use of energy. With regard
 372 to CE estimations, the difference remains observable: except for the heat wave period with an
 373 average CO₂ emissions factor of 0.31 kgCO₂/kWh, which remains closer to the BC value of 0.33
 374 kgCO₂/kWh. Whereas, for instance, the rest of the values are 40% (pre-pandemic with 0.21
 375 kgCO₂/kWh) to 45% (intense snow with 0.14 kgCO₂/kWh) below the building code value.
 376 Therefore, it can be concluded that if one had made use of the factors from building assessment
 377 codes to estimate the CE they would have overestimated them with at least 40% of difference. The
 378 estimation of PE presents very similar values around 2.3 for both CFs from BC and hourly
 379 methods, only in intense snow the hourly method is slightly above the CF from BC.

Table 6: Overall results. Impact of hourly rates in extreme events: Hourly CO2 emissions, PE use and PVPC for the COVID19 (2020) compared to pre-pandemic (2019), heat wave (2018) and post-pandemic (2021).

Period	Dates	Year	Penalty signals λ (penalty unit C_n /kWh)			
			AEF [kgCO2/kWh]	APEF		PVPC
				[kWh_pe/kWh]		[€/kWh]
				Nren	Total	(avg)
Heat wave	July 29 th – August 11 th	2018	0.31	1.84	2.29	106.60
Pre-pandemic	March 14 th – August 7 th	2019	0.21	1.81	2.26	91.22
Pandemic	March 14 th – August 7 th	2020	0.17	1.76	2.29	65.67
Post-pandemic	March 14 th – August 7 th	2021	0.16	1.60	2.20	129.23
Intense snow	January 9 th – January 10 th	2021	0.14	1.72	2.43	127.22
CFs from Building Codes			0.33	1.95	2.37	

380

381 4.2.1. Accumulated CO2 emissions (kgCO2) and primary energy (kWhpe)

382 Figure 4 presents the results for the equivalent emissions in kgCO2 eq. and primary energy use
383 kWhpe eq. associated with the aggregated consumption profile throughout the whole period. The
384 analysis reveals that hourly CE and PE are more accurately computed with hourly temporal
385 resolution, as they capture the variability of the electric grid and perform dynamically depending
386 on grid behavior. There is a larger difference in the magnitude of emission rates as years passed
387 by, and more specifically over the COVID19 period. The AEF values are almost half of the
388 constant one proposed by the building code in the pandemic period, whereas there is less difference
389 in the magnitude of primary energy rates. Indeed, for some hours, the values of primary energy
390 conversion factors are larger than the constant one proposed by the building code, especially during
391 the night. This can be explained by the structure of the electricity mix in Spain which used nuclear
392 power plants as the base systems in the mix. As load decreases during the nights, the share of
393 electricity generated from nuclear becomes higher, so primary energy factor in the night are the
394 high-ones. However, this cannot be observed in the emissions factors as nuclear is a free-emissions
395 technology. The reduction of average factors during the last years is due to the higher penetration
396 of renewables in the electricity system (mainly wind and solar) while displacing more polluting
397 technologies like coal power plants.

Figure 4: Emission and primary energy equivalent measured in kgCO₂ eq. and kWh_{pe} eq. respectively for the whole period considered (from January 1st 2018 to December 31st 2021). Right quadrants show a zoom in for some days during 2020 lockdown period.

398

399 The summarized consumption profile is then assessed with the factors obtained for each period
 400 and analyzed as well applying the building codes so the difference can be observed. The dynamic
 401 behavior of hourly factors is highlighted above, reflecting how they capture, depending on period
 402 characteristics, the grid variability. We would then analyze how the use of factors with hourly
 403 resolution can lead to a very different view of the significance of interventions than the system
 404 average rate.

405 Table 7 presents the overall results for the analysis periods. They quantify the difference of the
 406 estimation if one makes use of hourly conversion factors. This consumption assessment reflects
 407 the variation that a building associated kCO₂ eq. and kWh_{pe} eq. experiences depending on the
 408 grid variability at a concrete period.

Table 7: Overall results. Impact of hourly rates in emissions estimation for the consumption profile. The variation from hourly to constant accumulated penalties presented in percentage.

Consumption Assessment	CO ₂ Emissions	Primary energy use						Energy cost [€]
				Total		Non-renewable		
		Elec.Use [kWh]	kgCO ₂ Hourly	kgCO ₂ Constant	kWh_pe Hourly	kWh_pe Constant	kWh_pe Hourly	
Heat wave	257.56	80.19	85.25	586.12	609.90	469.66	503.27	29.21
Pre-pandemic	648.98	137.64	214.81	1458.03	1536.80	1160.73	1268.11	63.50
Pandemic	726.91	120.30	240.61	1639.57	1721.33	1215.89	1420.39	52.58
Post-pandemic	662.53	102.59	219.30	1438.90	1568.87	1034.68	1294.58	89.02
Intense snow	19.47	2.84	6.45	46.17	46.11	32.60	38.05	2.78

Variations from hourly to constant in percentage			
Period	CE	Total PE	Nren PE
Heat wave	+6%	+4%	+7%
Pre-pandemic	+36%	+5%	+9%
Pandemic	+50%	+5%	+14%
Post-pandemic	+53%	+8%	+20%
Intense snow	+56%	-0.1%	+14%

409

410 As a general conclusion, it is perceived in Table 7 that quantifying the accumulated CO₂ emissions
 411 (kgCO₂) and the primary energy use (kWhpe) is assessed properly when making use of hourly
 412 signals as inputs to compute penalty units. For all the periods considered, emissions and primary
 413 energy would have been overestimated except for intense snow primary energy (kWhpe).

414 In terms of **accumulated CO₂ emissions (kgCO₂ eq.)**, if computed making use of factors from
 415 building codes (BC) the final emissions would have been overestimated by 50% (pandemic, post-
 416 pandemic and intense snow) and by 30% (pre-pandemic). The smaller difference is appreciated
 417 over the heat wave period, where the variation remains overestimated just by 6%.

418 In terms of **accumulated total primary energy (kWhpe eq.)**, if computed making use of building
 419 codes (BC) the final primary energy would have been overestimated by a smaller percentage than

420 the presented by emissions, ranging from 4% to 8%, except for the period of intense snow where
 421 they would have been underestimated by 0.1%.

422 In terms of **accumulated non-renewable primary energy (kWhpe eq.)**, if computed making use
 423 of building codes (BC) the final primary energy would have been overestimated by a smaller
 424 percentage than the one presented by emissions, ranging from 6% to 20%.

425 For periods with overestimation of emissions and primary energy, the average emissions factor
 426 (AEF) mean remains much lower than the building codes (BC), which reflects that a hourly
 427 conversion factor takes into account the variability at hour of the grid, a better estimation to
 428 characterize the energy efficiency of a building at an emissions level. Whilst to estimate the
 429 primary energy use associated, it presents two different behaviors: for total primary energy, an
 430 overestimation is observed through all periods, but for non-renewable an exception for the intense
 431 snow period is presented with an underestimation.

432 4.2.2 Extreme weather scenarios

433 The intense snow period presented in Figure 6 offers larger amplitude than the heat wave period
 434 from Figure 5. Accumulated penalty of emissions for intense snow periods is 40% larger, and
 435 accumulated total primary energy 8%. Whilst for the non-renewable primary energy, the amplitude
 436 remains larger for the heat wave period.

Figure 5: Impact of hourly rates in emissions and primary energy estimation during the heatwave (2018) the aggregated consumption profile.

Figure 6: Impact of hourly rates in emissions and primary energy estimation during the intense snow (2021) for the aggregated consumption profile.

437 4.2.3 COVID19 scenario

438 The pandemic (2020) lockdown is studied through this section as a unusual period to be
 439 investigated. The same period is compared for 2019 (pre-pandemic) and 2021 (post-pandemic).
 440 Overall results from Table 8 reflect that in this concrete period of the year, the average hourly
 441 emissions factor estimates about 46% less kgCO₂/kWh than the factors from building codes (BC).
 442 For the average Nren APEF, it estimates about 8% less than the BC, and in terms of total APEF
 443 the average is 3% lower than the BC.

Table 8: Overall results. Impact of hourly rates in extreme events: Hourly CE, PE and PVPC for the period of lockdown (2020) compared to the same period in pre-pandemic (2019), and post-pandemic (2021).

Lockdown March 14 th – May 4 th	Penalty signals λ (penalty unit C_n /kWh)			
	AEF [kgCO ₂ /kWh]	APEF [kWh_pe/kWh]		PVPC [€/kWh]
		Nren	Total	
2019	0.18	1.82	2.33	93.61
2020	0.14	1.77	2.39	60.71
2021	0.15	1.60	2.24	104.26
CFs from BC	0.33	1.95	2.37	

444

445 Table 9 showcases the accumulated penalties. Accumulated electricity use over the pandemic was
 446 22% higher than in 2019 and 11% compared to 2021. Accumulated CO₂ emissions follow the

447 same pattern than the overall results (50% overestimation if applied BC) for the whole period from
 448 lockdown to reopening, reflecting that the lockdown (March 14th – May 4th) was the period that
 449 established the behavior of the whole period (March 14th – August 7th). Accumulated total primary
 450 energy follows the same pattern although the variations remain lower. Accumulated non-
 451 renewable primary energy remains the same, except for the pandemic lockdown which reflects
 452 lower variation.

453

Table 9: Impact of hourly rates in emissions estimation for the consumption profile. Lockdown assessment. The variation from hourly to constant accumulated penalties presented in percentage.

Lockdown		CO ₂ Emissions		Primary energy use				Energy cost [€]
				Total		Non-renewable		
Period	Elec.Use [kWh]	kgCO ₂ Hourly	kgCO ₂ Constant	kWh_pe Hourly	kWh_pe Constant	kWh_pe Hourly	kWh_pe Constant	
2019	228.996	41.974	75.798	527.343	542.263	409.003	447.459	23.023
2020	291.185	41.106	96.382	682.89	689.526	501.149	568.975	20.173
2021	258.933	38.677	85.707	569.17	613.154	401.222	505.956	28.757

Variations from hourly to constant in percentage			
Period	CE	Total PE	Nren PE
2019	+45%	+3%	+9%
2020	+57%	+1%	+12%
2021	+55%	+7%	+21%

454

455 4.3 Case 2

456 As the results of the flexibility assessments might offer a different view of the implementation of
 457 the strategy, results are investigated first for the whole year of 2018, then splitted in heating and
 458 cooling months (representative) for potential differences.

459 4.3.1 Results for 2018

460 The computation of hourly signals to use them as inputs to activate energy flexibility in buildings
 461 is assessed through this section. The overall results for the analysis of the whole year of 2018 is
 462 presented in Table 10. First, it is observed that hourly rates better capture the variability of the
 463 electric grid for 2018 compared to factors from building codes (BC), although they seem quite
 464 close (in the previous section it was observed that for 2018 the values seemed to be closer than
 465 upcoming years). Indeed, if one had made use of factors from BC the results would have been
 466 overestimated with a 14.8% for carbon emissions (CE) estimations and with 1% for primary energy
 467 (PE) assessment. Overestimations present a higher difference in emissions estimation, as it was
 468 declared over the previous sections. On the other hand, this period presents an average PVPC of
 469 0.103 €/kWh and 39% of renewable generation sources (RES). This period presents an
 470 accumulated energy consumption for HVAC systems of 1324.130 kWh and for total appliances of
 471 4331.267 kWh.

Table 10: Input signals (average values) for the whole year of 2018.

	Penalty signals λ (penalty unit C_n /kWh)				Consumption E
	<i>AEF</i> [kgCO2/kWh]	<i>APEF</i> [kWh_pe/kWh]	<i>PVPC</i> [€/kWh]	<i>RES</i> [%]	<i>HVAC</i> [kWh]
2018	0.28	1.93	0.10	0.39	1324.13
CFs from BC	0.33	1.95			

472

473 Figure 7 illustrates the determination process of the penalty signals considered. PVPC is retrieved
 474 from ESIOS already provided with hourly resolution. Hourly AEF and APEF are computed
 475 following the steps detailed in the previous work (Álvarez, 2022). RES is computed mapping the
 476 production technologies to obtain the global RES ratio. The modulation signals obtained from
 477 these different input penalty signals are shown on the bottom graphs of *Figure 7*, and will later be
 478 applied to the indoor setpoint to activate energy flexibility.

Figure 7: Determination process of penalty signals.

479

480 The results of simulations are presented in Table 11. Results are for the whole year of 2018 and
 481 they are presented as absolute values for the base and flexible cases. Variations are presented in
 482 percentage. Results are investigated in terms of applying it to HVAC systems. In this sense, results
 483 are presented for the base case (0-Reference, $[C_0]$ Accumulated penalty of base case, penalty unit)
 484 and the flexible cases (1-AEF $[\text{kgCO}_2/\text{kWh}]$ modulation , 2-APEF $[\text{kWh}_{pe}/\text{kWh}]$ modulation,
 485 3-PVPC $[\text{€}/\text{kWh}]$ modulation, 4-RES share $[\%]$ modulation). The results therefore will showcase:

- 486 a) $[C_E]$: The accumulated electricity use expressed in kWh
- 487 b) $[C_{AEF}]$: The accumulated CO2 emissions expressed in kgCO_2
- 488 c) $[C_{APEF}]$: The accumulated Primary energy expressed in kWh_{pe}
- 489 d) $[C_{PVPC}]$: The accumulated Energy cost expressed in EUR

Table 11: Results for the whole year of 2018. Absolute values for the base case and flexible cases. Variations in percentage.

Case	Control strategies: penalty signals modulation				
Penalty units eq.	0-Reference	1-AEF	2-APEF	3-PVPC	4-RES
[C _E] Elec. Use [kW]	1324.13	1347.27 (+1.7%)	<i>1382.68</i> (+4.4%)	1346.34 (+1.7%)	1367.09 (+3.2%)
	FI	-0.02	-0.04	-0.02	-0.03
[C _{AEF}] CO ₂ emissions [kgCO ₂]	398.21	391.93 (-1.6%)	<i>410.02</i> (+3%)	398.68 (+0.1%)	401.70 (+0.9%)
	FI	0.02	-0.03	-0.001	-0.01
[C _{APEF}] Primary energy [kWh _{pe}]	2559.31	2593.44 (+1.3%)	2631.06 (+2.8%)	<i>2647.93</i> (+3.5%)	2609.73 (+2%)
	FI	-0.01	-0.03	-0.03	-0.02
[C _{PVPC}] Energy cost [€]	147.66	149.27 (+1.1%)	<i>157.37</i> (+6.6%)	138.39 (-6.3%)	154.86 (+4.9%)
	FI	-0.01	-0.07	0.06	-0.05

490 Table 11 showcases the results for the simulation of the building over 2018. Results marked in
 491 bold indicate the best strategy to reduce the equivalence penalty unit. Italic results indicate the
 492 worst strategies to follow if one wanted to reduce the accumulated penalty unit considered.

493 The values from Table 11 indicate that two modulation strategies offer benefits for each specific
 494 goal. Flexible scenarios such as the AEF and PVPC modulation result in improvement compared
 495 to the base scenario. To reduce CO₂ emissions, if an AEF modulation strategy is applied they
 496 could be reduced by 1.6%. To reduce energy costs (EC), if applied to the PVPC modulation
 497 strategy it could be reduced by 6.3%.

498 A significant result is also observed with the APEF modulation, being the worst performing in the
 499 reduction of all the considered penalty units. Indeed, it does not reach its specific goal of reducing
 500 the accumulated primary energy of the period, it increases it being the second worse in that matter.
 501 This result concludes that APEF modulation does not serve as a control strategy that can be used
 502 to activate energy flexibility in buildings, neither towards environmental or economic goals,
 503 mostly because its signal does not present sufficient fluctuations that would enable an optimization
 504 process to make the most of it.

505 In Table 11 is shown the flexibility index for each case. The results clearly show a non-favorable
 506 scenario to activate energy flexibility in most cases. For the majority of cases proposed their FI

507 not only is equal to 0, it is even reaching negative values, which indicates a non-favorable scenario
 508 to activate energy flexibility as they not only offer zero improvement but they get worse than the
 509 base case.

510 As already perceived, AEF and PVPC modulations, respectively with FI of 0.02 and FI of 0.06,
 511 are the only ones that get a positive FI indicating that for each specific goal (CO2 reduction and
 512 PVPC reduction): they perform better than the base scenario, where the accumulated penalty is
 513 smaller.

514 Figure 8 illustrates the accumulated penalty unit for each case. It can be appreciated how the PVPC
 515 modulation offers larger variations. In this sense, if applying AEF or PVPC flexibility cases to a
 516 household to control the HVAC system it can lead to benefits. Even though the fractional savings
 517 that are possible to achieve when applying the flexibility control strategies seem quite small.
 518

Figure 8: Accumulated energy (top-left) and accumulated penalty of the base case and the flexible scenarios.

519 In the following sections, 4.3.2 and 4.3.3, the data is splitted between heating and cooling seasons.
 520 For the heating season, the months considered include October to May. Cooling season includes

521 April to November. Table 12 shows the average results for each month representative of the
 522 heating and cooling season, February and July respectively. These periods are considered with
 523 higher demand than the others. It is observed that the hourly CE signal (AEF) is quite similar for
 524 both months with a difference of 0.03 kgCO₂/kWh, whilst for the hourly PE signal (APEF) the
 525 difference is 0.28 kWh_{pe}/kWh. PVPC and RES remain the same. The winter demand of February
 526 reaches 64% more of accumulated consumption.

Table 12: Input signals for the whole month of February and June of 2018.

	Penalty signals λ (penalty unit C _n /kWh) (average)				Accumulated
	<i>AEF</i>	<i>APEF</i>	<i>PVPC</i>	<i>RES</i>	Consumption
	[kgCO ₂ /kWh]	[kWh _{pe} /kWh]	[€/kWh]	[%]	[kWh]
February	0.3	2.06	100.34	38	212.61
July	0.27	1.78	102.75	39	77.59

527 4.3.2 Results for February 2018

528 There is a very profoundly observable difference between the results obtained for the whole year
 529 (see Table 11) and the ones obtained in Table 13. What brings attention is the RES modulation
 530 strategy. RES modulation appears to perform the best results in terms of reducing the accumulated
 531 electricity use (-0.4%), the CO₂ emissions (-8%), the primary energy use (-5.3%) and the energy
 532 cost (-2%). Although the energy cost is being reduced, other modulation strategies reach the goal
 533 better: such as the proposed PVPC signal, reaching a reduction of 13% and the AEF signal,
 534 reaching a 2.2% reduction.

Table 13: Results for February (2018). Absolute values for the base case and flexible cases. Variations in percentage.

Case	Control strategies: penalty signals modulation				
Penalty units eq.	0-Reference	1-AEF	2-APEF	3-PVPC	4-RES
	212.61	207.78	216.55	219.43	205.26
[C _E] Elec. Use [kW]		-2.3%	1.8%	3.1%	-3.6%
	FI	0.02	-0.02	-0.03	0.04
	65.73	60.62	65.45	66.24	60.91
[C _{AEF}] CO ₂ emissions [kgCO ₂]		-8.4%	-0.4%	0.8%	-7.9%
	FI	0.08	0.004	-0.01	0.07

	421.27	409.71	419.04	461.94	400.19
[C _{APEF}] Primary energy [kWh _{pe}]		-2.8%	-0.5%	8.8%	-5.3%
	FI	0.02	0.01	-0.1	0.05
	20.05	19.61	21.29	17.74	19.67
[C _{PVPC}] Energy cost [€]		-2.2%	5.8%	-13%	-2%
	FI	0.02	-0.06	0.12	0.02

535

536 Moreover, Table 13 results bring a different view of the significance of the flexibility strategies.
537 For electricity use reduction, AEF and RES modulation would reach its goal. To reduce the
538 accumulated CO₂, either AEF or RES modulation also would impact. For primary energy
539 reduction of non-renewable sources, we find that RES, followed by AEF and APEF would help.
540 In this sense, results with APEF modulation remain only favorable as a flexibility strategy for
541 February compared with the whole year analysis. For energy cost (EC) reduction, we find that
542 PVPC, followed by AEF and RES would reduce the cost we pay for our electricity, by up to 13%.

543 The more impactful flexibility strategies depending on their FI would be the one proposed by AEF
544 modulation, reaching a reduction of 8.4% the CO₂ emissions and a FI of 0.08, which indicates that
545 this scenario makes the penalty to be smaller than the base scenario. For the PVPC modulation
546 strategy, a FI of 0.12 indicates quite a big difference compared with the base scenario.

547 4.3.3 Results for July 2018

548 Table 14 showcases the results for the month of July. It can be appreciated to have a different view
549 of the flexibility scenarios. For this month representing the Summer season, we find that a PVPC
550 modulation would offer the best outcomes if implementing a flexibility scenario compared to the
551 base case, with a cost reduction of 15.6%. It is perceived as an improvement throughout all the
552 accumulated penalty units. Flexibility index is also performing with its best results: for
553 accumulated electricity use and EC, PVPC modulation is the only that improves with the
554 implementation of a flexibility strategy resulting in positive FI of 0.06 and 0.14. For the reduction
555 of accumulated CE and PE, the difference with the APEF modulation is observable. Although we
556 also find here that APEF modulation in this sense obtains a positive FI which indicates that there
557 is a slightly better performance compared to the base scenario.

Table 14: Results for July (2018). Absolute values for the base case and flexible cases. Variations in percentage.

Case	Control strategies: penalty signals modulation				
Penalty units eq.	0-Reference	1-AEF	2-APEF	3-PVPC	4-RES

	77.586	82.40	78.24	72.63	82.26
[C _E] Elec. Use [kW]		5.9%	0.8%	-6.8%	5.7%
	FI	-0.06	-0.01	0.06	-0.06
	21.19	21.56	21.1	19.57	21.83
[C _{AEF}] CO ₂ emissions [kgCO ₂]		1.7%	-0.5%	-8.3%	2.9%
	FI	-0.02	0.01	0.08	-0.03
	138.09	144.18	137.49	129.27	144.15
[C _{APFC}] Primary energy [kWh _{pe}]		4.2%	-0.4%	-6.8%	4.2%
	FI	-0.04	0.01	0.06	-0.04
	9.2	9.69	9.48	7.96	9.83
[C _{PVPC}] Energy cost [€]		5.1%	3%	-15.6%	6.4%
	FI	-0.06	-0.03	0.14	-0.07

558

559 The implemented flexibility strategy performs favorable in high demand periods (represented by
560 February and July). However, in periods of low demand, results show that the strategy is not so
561 efficient, concluding that if the whole year is considered, they would offer lower benefits.

562 5 DISCUSSION AND FURTHER WORK

563 An in depth analysis for the rest of the months could be valuable to create a final flexibility strategy
564 to implement and thus reduce the objective penalty units of accumulated electricity, CO₂, primary
565 energy and energy cost. In this sense, developing a model that can activate energy flexibility
566 depending on the actual demand, when higher, would lead to bigger reductions. Due to what is
567 perceived in this work, if compared the whole 2018 analysis to February analysis, AEF and RES
568 modulation results would offer not only reductions in accumulated specific goals but in all of the
569 penalty units considered. In regard to July analysis, each modulation performs better, offering
570 larger benefits accumulating less electricity used, carbon emissions, primary energy and energy
571 cost.

572 The flexibility strategies can be applied to other significant months of the year with a deeper
573 analysis, and even to further years to investigate potential differences. Marginal signals can be
574 used as input signals to be compared with the obtained results and thus, observe the carbon
575 emissions and primary energy savings due to marginal variations, as remarked by Peán (2018).
576 The next steps would also be to implement the methodology in a real building, where smart control

577 systems are used to act on real time and shift the demand, intervening with reductions in electricity
578 use, CO₂ emissions, primary energy or cost for the flexible building using them.

579 The results showed that greater savings or benefits were achieved in selected months, compared
580 to the accumulated results of the whole year. These specific months were the ones of high thermal
581 demand, whether it being heating or cooling demand. In that case, the modulation strategy
582 effectively displaces the load towards low penalty periods. In shoulder season periods, this strategy
583 proves to be less effective: in fact, the upwards modulation of the set-point in the hours of low
584 penalty provokes an increase of the thermal demand that was previously low, and this stored energy
585 is not really used afterwards, resulting in the downwards modulation being practically ineffective.
586 It is suggested that in those times of low demand, only the downwards modulation in times of high
587 penalty should be applied for better results.

588 Another aspect to be discussed is the source of the conversion factors for each technology, as
589 reported in Table 1. Some of the references where the values of these factors have been picked
590 date back 10 or 12 years from the writing of the present article, which is an important time span.
591 However, the main sources of information like the IPCC reports have not been updated more
592 recently, and it is believed that most mature technologies have not evolved so importantly as to
593 make their emissions or primary energy use change drastically.

594 **6 CONCLUSIONS**

595 Housing contributes to the largest proportions of CO₂ emissions and primary energy use rather
596 than other sectors, which requires attention to implement mechanisms that help in the reduction of
597 carbon emissions and the development of accurate assessments for the impact of potential
598 interventions.

599 The conversion factors retrieved from building assessment codes for electricity are used to convert
600 the final electricity use to equivalent emissions and primary energy. They should be specific to the
601 generators of each fuel type or technology in each region, but they are annual-average values.
602 Using a constant value does not allow to capture seasonal, daily or hourly variation in emission
603 and primary energy intensity. These conversion factors are also released with year lags (the latest
604 provided for Spain is in 2014), therefore they will not reflect recent changes in the mix of sources.

605 The present work has shown that the use of hourly conversion factors that are dynamic over the
606 year better captures the variability of the electricity grid. Hour variability includes technologies,
607 imports and losses. They can be affected by the amount of renewables, the consumption demand
608 and the conversion factors from different sources, which can vary with extreme weather periods
609 or other exceptional events that are difficult to predict.

610 On one hand, the results reflect that the amount of emissions that a building might produce when
611 consuming electricity are more accurate if assessed making use of hourly conversion factors, as
612 they lead to proper estimates due to the period subset characteristics of the electric grid. Factors

613 retrieved from building codes overestimate the carbon emissions associated consumption, with a
614 50% difference and the result of not capturing the variability and dynamic behavior of the grid. In
615 this sense, CO₂ emission factors that governments provide should be up to date and reflect this
616 variability to reflect accurate emissions for future assessments. Documentation, reports and
617 databases are needed to offer the private and public sector better analysis and implementation. The
618 energy mix evolves in a way that a more realistic assessment with hourly resolution should be
619 provided. It is also interesting to see that the emissions have decreased importantly during the
620 COVID19 lockdown despite a surge in domestic loads from people working from home. The
621 period of heat wave corresponded to the higher emissions level, while the period of intense snow
622 corresponded to low emissions.

623 On the other hand, the fact that primary energy use assessments present results that differ less from
624 hourly to constant estimations could be due to the update of the existing information, the
625 consideration of the participation of different sources to a primary energy assessment. The
626 estimation of the total and non-renewable energy use might have not varied from the year that the
627 building codes were updated, which is very close to the hourly estimation for each period with the
628 highest difference being 20% overestimated. Although the average and hourly values for primary
629 energy differ less, it is important to note that the hourly profile of primary energy factor during a
630 day varies significantly, with a valley during noon hours, hence providing potential to move
631 demand towards these hours.

632 As years pass by, there is a move towards a cleaner energy mix. Cleaner fossil fuel technologies,
633 with relatively lower emission factors are increasing their use and the share of RES has improved
634 its penetration. The accumulated CO₂ emissions and primary energy use from consumers is then
635 decreasing year by year. The results for the accumulated penalties showcase that the accumulated
636 electricity use exhibited a greater growth than the household accumulated CO₂ emissions, due to
637 the energy mix incorporating more renewables and cleaner fossil fuel technologies in recent years.
638 This can be also perceived that the emissions factor is relatively lower throughout the years. The
639 same behavior remains for accumulated primary energy penalties.

640 Demand-response mechanisms such as energy flexibility studied through this work might help in
641 the reduction of carbon emissions and primary energy consumption accumulated penalties.
642 Depending if the goal is to shift the demand due to environmental or economical reasons, a
643 different modulation should be applied. In general, each penalty signal reaches improvements on
644 its direct penalty unit (i.e. AEF modulation would help in reducing accumulated CO₂ emissions),
645 but other goals might be affected negatively (i.e. increasing the electricity used, primary energy or
646 energy cost). Higher optimization of energy flexibility might be seen when developing models that
647 take into account the month of the year; not only due to larger variations in improvement of
648 reduction of the penalty, but also because this allows to select between different modulations at
649 months of the year that best fits for the behavior of the electric grid and the household consumption.

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